

An Efficient Implementation of the Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter

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Charlotte Hermann

Abstract—In Random Finite Set based multi-sensor multi-object tracking, the NP-hard measurement-to-track assignment problem is a key challenge. One approach to address this challenge involves executing computationally simpler single-sensor updates based on a common prediction, followed by the fusion of these updates. This strategy is used by the already proposed Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli filter, which still poses computational challenges in its existing formulation. This paper introduces an efficient implementation of the Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli filter by improving the efficiency of the individual single-sensor updates and the fusion of the resulting single-sensor posterior densities. Two different approaches are presented for each part, including the new *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm, which solves a k shortest path problem on highly structured graphs. Our approach is evaluated on simulations, and the results are compared with an Iterated Corrector implementation of the Labeled Multi-Bernoulli filter using comparable simplifications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-sensor multi-object tracking serves diverse applications, addressing scenarios where estimating trajectories for a variable and unknown number of objects using measurements of multiple sensors is essential [1], [2]. Random Finite Sets (RFSs) provide a mathematical framework to address this task [2]. Several filters based on RFSs are already well established, including the Generalized Labeled Multi-Bernoulli (GLMB) and Labeled Multi-Bernoulli (LMB) filters, where the latter in particular provides an efficient approximation of the posterior GLMB density [3] and has been successfully demonstrated in real-world applications [4]. The LMB filter uses the update of the GLMB filter. Therefore, it also faces the challenge of the NP-hard multi-sensor update [5]. Several approaches have been developed to address this problem [5]–[9]. Generally, all methods involve a trade-off between tracking performance and computation time. The objective is to achieve the best tracking performance while minimizing computational complexity. Approaches based on the Bayes Parallel Combination Rule (BPCR) [6]–[9] can be used for synchronized sensors. They involve separately calculating individual sensor updates based on a common prediction

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followed by subsequent fusion and are well-suited for this purpose. These methods allow for both a Bayes-optimal result and a computationally efficient implementation. The computational efficiency is achieved by decomposing the NP-hard multi-sensor data association problem into computable single-sensor data association problems. Furthermore, the parallel computation of the updates is enabled, and, compared to other approaches in the literature, the filter result does not depend on the sensor order [6], [8]. Among the filters based on the BPCR, the Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli (FPM-LMB) filter [8] stands out from a computational point of view, as it uses efficient LMB filter single-sensor updates and also contains a comparatively computational efficient fusion. However, improvements in computational performance are still needed to make the filter suitable for real-world applications.

This paper proposes an efficient implementation of the FPM-LMB filter from [8]. The idea is to reduce both the computational complexity of the single-sensor updates and the computational complexity of the fusion. In the calculation of single-sensor LMB updates, there are two main challenges: the transformation of the LMB density into a GLMB density in cases with many tracks in the LMB density and the data association problem. This paper proposes two variants for solving these problems. One is to use the already published Gibbs sampler [10], which solves both issues simultaneously. The other variant treats the LMB to GLMB density transformation as a k shortest path problem and solves it with the *kBestSelection* algorithm [6]. The data association problem is then solved using the Murty ranked assignment algorithm [11]. Besides, grouping [3] is also implemented for both variants. Furthermore, the efficiency of the spatial distribution fusion is increased. For this purpose, the spatial distribution fusion can also be considered as a k shortest path problem and solved in two different ways. In the first variant, the problem is solved using the *kBestSelection* algorithm [6], which has the disadvantage that it does not compute the actual k best solutions, as will be shown later. The second variant, on the other hand, calculates the actual k best solutions using the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm proposed in this paper.

To summarize our work in this paper, after discussing related work in Section II and introducing the necessary basics in Section III, we propose:

- a more efficient implementation of the single-sensor LMB updates of the FPM-LMB filter by solving the k shortest path problem of the LMB to GLMB transformation or by using the known Gibbs sampler in Section IV,

- a generalization of the *kBestSelection* algorithm for solving highly structured graphs, called the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm, in Section V, and
- formulation of the FPM-LMB fusion of spatial densities as a *k* shortest path problem and solving it using the *kBestSelection* or the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm in Section V.

The paper closes with a detailed evaluation in Section VI and some conclusions in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

For the LMB [3] and GLMB [12] filters, efficient implementations are already known [7], [10], [13], [14]. In Gibbs sampling-based approaches [10], [13], the key idea is to sample an arbitrary number of hypotheses based on a distribution rather than calculating all possible hypotheses in the update step. This simplifies the data association problem and eliminates the need to generate predicted GLMB hypotheses, resulting in a joint prediction and update process. Efficient implementations based on Belief Propagation (BP) with a focus on the LMB filter are presented in [7], [14]. The complexity is lower than with Gibbs sampling-based approaches, and the tracking performance is comparable or better [14].

There are several ways to include multiple sensors in RFS based trackers. One possibility are sub-optimal track-to-track fusion approaches [2], [15]. Centralized tracking architectures offer another possibility. Here, a Fusion Center (FC) processes the measurements of all sensors with the help of a central tracker [16], with the NP-hard data association problem being a challenge [17]. Three different strategies are possible to tackle this challenge: The Iterated Corrector (IC) approach [5], [7], sampling-based approaches [5], [7], and approaches based on the BPCR [2], [6], [7].

The idea behind the IC approach is straightforward. Single-sensor updates for the individual sensors are carried out iteratively. An example of this is the IC-LMB (IC-LMB) filter [8], [9], which performs an LMB prediction and then iteratively performs the single-sensor LMB filter updates. The disadvantage of this approach is that the result depends on the sensor sequence due to the intermediate approximations required for computability. In [5], a sampling-based approach is presented. This has the potential for better tracking performance than the IC approaches, but sometimes requires more computing time [7]. Additionally, both the IC-based and the sampling-based approach share the drawback of not allowing parallelization of individual single-sensor updates.

Approaches based on the BPCR were introduced in [6], [18] with the Product Multi-Sensor GLMB (PM-GLMB), in [9] with the Product Multi-Sensor LMB (PM-LMB), in [7] with the Parallel Update multi-sensor LMB (PU-LMB), and in [8] with the FPM-LMB filter, among others. These calculate single-sensor updates in parallel based on a common prediction and then fuse the result. The FPM-LMB filter stands out in terms of low computational complexity, as it uses efficient LMB filter updates for the single-sensor

updates. In the fusion, LMB densities are then fused, which is particularly efficient since only the spatial densities of the tracks and their existence probabilities need to be fused, in contrast to many hypotheses, as with the PM-GLMB and PM-LMB filters. In addition, no approximation of Gaussian mixtures to Gaussian distributions has to be performed as with the PU-LMB filter. Furthermore, efficient implementations known for single-sensor filters can be easily applied to the FPM-LMB filter. An efficient implementation for the fusion is only known for the PM-GLMB and the PM-LMB filter, where the *kBestSelection* algorithm [6] is used to compute the *k* likely best solutions based on the predicted GLMB hypotheses. However, such an implementation is not yet available for LMB densities needed for the FPM-LMB filter.

III. BACKGROUND AND NOTATION

This section introduces our notation following [6] and a summary of the required background.

A. Notation

Single objects are denoted by lowercase letters, where single-object states are represented by a vector x in a state space \mathbb{X} , and single-object measurements are denoted by a vector z in a measurement space \mathbb{Z} . The finite subsets of a multi-object state RFS X are given by $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X})$. Multiple objects are modeled using RFS [2] and are represented by uppercase letters, like the multi-object state $X \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X})$, or the multi-object measurement $Z \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{Z})$.

The active sensor is denoted by $s \in \{1, \dots, V\}$, where V represents the total number of sensors in use. Additionally, $\theta^{(s)} = I \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, |Z^{(s)}|\}$ represents a possible assignment of the set I of track labels to the measurements $Z^{(s)}$. Unique assignments are ensured by the property $\theta^{(s)}(i) = \theta^{(s)}(i') > 0 \Rightarrow i = i'$. Here, $\theta^{(s)}(i) = 0$ indicates a misdetection. The space $\Theta^{(s)}$ encompasses all possible assignments of measurements to track labels. Moreover, the following multi-sensor abbreviations are used: $z \triangleq (z^{(1)}, \dots, z^{(V)})$, $Z \triangleq (Z^{(1)}, \dots, Z^{(V)})$, $\theta \triangleq (\theta^{(1)}, \dots, \theta^{(V)})$, and $\Theta \triangleq \Theta^{(1)} \times \dots \times \Theta^{(V)}$.

State vectors augmented with a label $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ are indicated by boldface letters, where \mathbb{L} is a discrete space, resulting in the labeled single-object state $\mathbf{x} = (x, \ell)$. This facilitates the estimation of object trajectories. A labeled multi-object state $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}$ for n objects is a labeled RFS on the space $\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{L}$. Furthermore, predicted densities are marked by a '+' subscript.

B. The Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter

The FPM-LMB filter addresses the NP-hard LMB filter multi-sensor update by performing separate updates for each sensor using a common prediction and then fusing the resulting single-sensor posterior densities. The sensors must be synchronized. This method allows for parallel processing and ensures that the outcome is independent of the sequence in which the sensors are updated. Given $J_+^{(\ell)}$ prior Gaussian

Fig. 1. Visualization of the graph structure suitable for the $kBestSelection$ algorithm.

Mixture (GM) components with predicted component means $\hat{x}_+^{(\ell,j)}$, covariances $\underline{P}^{(\ell,j)}$, and weights $\alpha_+^{(\ell,j)}$ and single-sensor posterior GM component with means $\hat{x}^{(s,\ell,j,m)}$, covariances $\underline{P}^{(s,\ell,j)}$, and weights $\alpha^{(s,\ell,j,m)}$, the fused spatial distribution of a track with label ℓ is given by a GM

$$p^{(\ell)}(x) = \frac{1}{\eta_Z^{(\ell)}} \sum_{j=1}^{J_+^{(\ell)}} \left(\alpha_+^{(\ell,j)} \mathcal{N}\left(x; \hat{x}_+^{(\ell,j)}, \underline{P}^{(\ell,j)}\right) \right)^{(1-V)} \cdot \prod_{s=1}^V \sum_{m=0}^{|Z^{(s)}|} \alpha^{(s,\ell,j,m)} \mathcal{N}\left(x; \hat{x}^{(s,\ell,j,m)}, \underline{P}^{(s,\ell,j)}\right) \quad (1a)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\eta_Z^{(\ell)}} \sum_{j=1}^{J_+^{(\ell)}} \sum_{\theta \in \Theta} \alpha^{(\ell,j,\theta)}(Z) \mathcal{N}\left(x; \hat{x}^{(\ell,j,\theta)}, \underline{P}^{(\ell,j,\theta)}\right). \quad (1b)$$

The fused posterior GM components are given by their means $\hat{x}^{(\ell,j,\theta)}$ and covariances $\underline{P}^{(\ell,j,\theta)}$, and the mixture weight yields

$$\alpha^{(\ell,j,\theta)}(Z) = C_Z^{(\ell,j,\theta)} \frac{\prod_{s=1}^V \alpha^{(s,\ell,j,\theta^{(s)})}(Z^{(s)})}{\left(\alpha_+^{(\ell,j)}\right)^{(V-1)}}. \quad (1c)$$

The density is normalized by $\eta_Z^{(\ell)}$. For more background on how equation (1b) is obtained, see [8]. As discussed in [8], [18], the constant $C_Z^{(\ell,j,\theta)}$ is theoretically close to one but cannot be calculated in a numerically stable manner. Therefore, it is commonly set to one in practice. For more details, see [8].

C. The $kBestSelection$ Algorithm

The $kBestSelection$ algorithm [6] solves the k shortest path problem [19] for graphs with the special structure as shown in Fig. 1. Its objective is to find the k paths from node A_0 to A_V with the smallest weight. The number of edges $T^{(s)}$ between two vertices does not matter. Neither does the number of nodes. Each edge has a weight w_{sn} , and the red path gives a possible solution to the directed graph. The $kBestSelection$ algorithm then calculates the k best solutions using a row-wise sorted weight matrix, where each matrix element corresponds to the weight of an edge. The best solution is then automatically given by the first column of the matrix. For the graph given in Fig. 1, the

weight matrix for example is

$$\underline{W} = \begin{bmatrix} w_{11} & \cdots & \cdots & w_{1T^{(1)}} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ w_{21} & \cdots & w_{2T^{(2)}} & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & & & & & & \vdots \\ w_{V1} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & w_{VT^{(V)}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

For more details, see [6].

IV. IMPROVING THE SINGLE-SENSOR UPDATE'S EFFICIENCY

There are two ways to implement the single-sensor LMB update. In the first version [3], the transformation from prior LMB to prior GLMB density is calculated. In the case of a large number of tracks, this is especially challenging from a computational point of view, as $2^{|\mathbb{L}|}$ GLMB hypotheses have to be calculated. Subsequently, for each prior GLMB hypothesis, the data association problem is solved using, e.g., the Murty ranked assignment algorithm [3], [11] or a Gibbs sampler [10].

The second version focuses on approaches that formulate the data association problem based on the prior LMB density and provide the prior GLMB density as a solution. Here, the explicit calculation of the prior GLMB density, which is computationally demanding in the case of many tracks, is bypassed. However, the data association problem is more significant than in the first variant, as it is no longer solved only per prior GLMB hypothesis. Due to the computational complexity, only efficient implementations such as the Gibbs sampler [10] or belief propagation [7], [14], and not the Murty ranked assignment algorithm [11], are suitable. Furthermore, using grouping [3, Section IV] also reduces the complexity of the data association problem.

In [8], the FPM-LMB filter was proposed with the use of the first version and without the use of grouping. The structure of the FPM-LMB also allows the use of the second version and grouping without customization. Therefore, an implementation of the efficient second version using grouping and a Gibbs sampler is presented in Section VI. The implementation of the Gibbs sampler is the same as in [10], with the difference that if the same hypothesis is drawn f times in a row, the sampling is stopped. This increases the computational efficiency significantly. We also propose a more efficient implementation of the first version. For this purpose, transforming the prior LMB density to the prior GLMB density is considered as a k shortest path problem. This can then be solved using the $kBestSelection$ algorithm, where the k best prior GLMB hypotheses are calculated. In this case, the row-sorted weight matrix required for the algorithm consists of only two elements per row, namely $r_+^{(\ell)}$ and $1 - r_+^{(\ell)}$, where $r_+^{(\ell)}$ is the predicted existence probability of the track with label ℓ . The number of rows $|\mathbb{L}|$ corresponds to the number of labels given in the LMB density. The Murty algorithm [11] is used for the subsequent GLMB update. Grouping can also be used for this variant.

Fig. 2. Visualization of the graph structure suitable for the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm with $n_B, n_C, \dots \leq V$.

V. EFFICIENT FUSION OF THE SPATIALS POSTERIORES

As can be seen from Eq. (1), only Gaussian mixtures that originate from the same prior Gaussian mixture component are fused at the fusion step of the FPM-LMB filter. The resulting number of fused mixture components per prior id j (cf. Eq. (1a)), given by

$$M = \prod_{s=1}^V (|Z^{(s)}| + 1), \quad (3)$$

where each product term contains the number of sensor measurements and the misdetection, is, however, still computationally demanding and grows exponentially with the number of sensors and polynomially with the number of measurements. The complexity can be reduced by calculating only dominating instead of all possible GM components. In the following, such a solution based on the *kBestSelection* algorithm [6] is presented first. This has the disadvantage that it can only be applied independently per prior component j with a fixed $k_j < k$, where $\sum_j k_j = k$. Therefore, the computed k solutions are not necessarily the k best solutions. We then present the proposed *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm to overcome this, which provides the actual k best solutions.

A. Application of the *kBestSelection* Algorithm

As already mentioned, the *kBestSelection* algorithm can only calculate the best solutions per prior GM component. Given that a total of k solutions are to be calculated, then

$$k_j = \left\lfloor \alpha_+^{(\ell, j)} k \right\rfloor \quad (4)$$

solutions are calculated per prior GM component j using the procedure described in [6]. The row-wise sorted weight matrix for a label ℓ and prior GM component id j is given as in Eq. (2), where one row contains the single-sensor posterior weights $\alpha^{(s, \ell, j, \theta^{(s)})}(Z^{(s)})$ of sensor s and there are V rows in total.

B. The Proposed *GeneralizedKBestSelection* Algorithm

In contrast to the variant just described with the *kBestSelection* algorithm, which only considers the problem locally per prior GM id, the problem can also be considered globally. As with the *kBestSelection* algorithm in Fig. 1, the generalized problem can also be represented by a graph as

shown in Fig. 2, where subgraphs contain the solutions for each prior GM component id. All subgraphs are connected via an additional node “A”. Furthermore, the subgraphs can contain a different number of nodes, and there can be any number of edges between two nodes. A potential solution is marked in red. In the following, the algorithm’s procedure is illustrated through the motivated example of spatial posterior fusion during the FPM-LMB filter fusion.

In order to obtain the actual k best solutions, a set of u row-wise sorted matrices $W = \{W_1, \dots, W_u\}$ is needed. Each element of the matrix W_j corresponds to one possible single-sensor posterior GM component weight of prior GM component j except the first line, where the weight of the prior GM component j multiplied by a normalization constant $C_Z^{(\ell, j, \theta)}$ is located in the first column and zeros in the others. Fig. 3 shows an example of the weight matrix. A possible solution for (1c) can then be received by picking one element per row. The first column of each matrix W_j corresponds to the best solution for GM component id j , i.e., with the highest product weight. Note that each sensor can provide a different number $T^{(j, \theta^{(s)})}$ of posterior GM components for the prior GM component j .

Similar to the *kBestSelection* algorithm [6], the solutions to the problem in Fig. 2 can also be represented by an acyclic, directed, vertex-weighted, bipartite tree with u sorted sub-trees, where u corresponds to the number of prior GM components of the track. The first three levels of the graph are visualized in Fig. 4. The main difference of the generalized algorithm lies in the root node, visualized in green. In this case, the root node refers to individual sub-trees marked, e.g., in red and blue, each of which can be used independently as a solution to the *kBestSelection* algorithm. Considering the u sub-graphs, each node \mathcal{N}_{jn} with index n and level l , except the root node, contains a possible solution for Eq. (1c), i.e., a possible combination of GM components with id j of the V posterior tracks with label ℓ . This possible solution is decoded by an index vector v , where the d -th entry $y = (v)_d$ selects the GM component weight $(W_j)_{d, y}$. The root node only contains a list \mathcal{J} of indices of the u sorted matrices W_j with $j \in [1, \dots, u]$. The list \mathcal{J} is sorted by the highest product weight of each matrix W_j .

1) *The Algorithm:* A general overview of the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm is given in Algorithm 1. Due to efficiency reasons, the graph is only partially built during the algorithm. In the following, the built part of the graph is called discovered, whereas the unbuilt part is called undiscovered. In addition to the indices list \mathcal{J} , the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm also uses a list of selected nodes \mathcal{L} and a list of potentially selected nodes \mathcal{P} , just like the *kBestSelection* algorithm. The algorithm input is the set of u row-wise sorted weight matrices W and the desired number of selections, i.e., solutions, k . The algorithm then delivers a sorted list of selected nodes as output. Like the *kBestSelection* algorithm, the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* algorithm can be divided into graph initialization and search of the k best solutions.

$$\underline{W}_j = \begin{bmatrix} C_Z^{(\ell,j,\theta)} (\alpha_+^{(\ell,j)})^{(1-V)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \alpha^{(1,\ell,j,\theta_1^{(1)})}(Z^{(1)}) & \dots & \dots & \alpha^{(1,\ell,j,\theta^{(1)})}_{T(j,\theta^{(1)})}(Z^{(1)}) \\ \alpha^{(2,\ell,j,\theta_1^{(2)})}(Z^{(2)}) & \dots & \alpha^{(2,\ell,j,\theta^{(2)})}_{T(j,\theta^{(2)})}(Z^{(2)}) & 0 \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ \alpha^{(V-1,\ell,j,\theta_1^{(V-1)})}(Z^{(V-1)}) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \alpha^{(V,\ell,j,\theta_1^{(V)})}(Z^{(V)}) & \dots & \dots & \alpha^{(V,\ell,j,\theta^{(V)})}_{T(j,\theta^{(V)})}(Z^{(V)}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{matrix} - \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ V-1 \\ V \end{matrix} \left. \vphantom{\begin{matrix} - \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ V-1 \\ V \end{matrix}} \right\} \text{sensor number}$$

Fig. 3. Exemplary weight matrix \underline{W}_j for the fusion of single-sensor posterior GM components $\alpha^{(s,\ell,j,\theta^{(s)})}(Z^{(s)})$ from V sensors based on a common prior mixture component with id j visualized in orange.

Fig. 4. First three levels of the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* tree for V sensors and u prior GM components. The root node N_{00} only contains the information about how the sub-trees are connected.

Algorithm 1: *GeneralizedKBestSelection*

Input: $W, k, \underline{\alpha}_+$

Output: \mathcal{L} % sorted list of selected nodes

```

# Initialize Tree                                     ▷  $\mathcal{O}(u \log u)$ 
 $V = \text{size}(\underline{W}_1, 1) = \dots = \text{size}(\underline{W}_u, 1)$            ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
 $u = |\underline{W}|$                                              ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
for  $j = 1 : u$  do                                     ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
     $\underline{W}_j = (\underline{W}_j)_{1:V,1:k}$                              ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
end for
 $\mathcal{J} = \text{initSortedIndicesList}(W, \underline{\alpha}_+)$                ▷  $\mathcal{O}(u \log(u))$ 
 $isRootNode = \text{True}$                                    ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
 $rootNode = \text{createRootNode}(\mathcal{J}, isRootNode)$          ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
 $\mathcal{L}.\text{init}(rootNode)$                                  ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
 $\mathcal{P}.\text{init}(rootNode.\text{nextBestChild}(\underline{A}, \mathcal{J}, \underline{\alpha}_+))$    ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 

# Find  $k$  Best Selections                             ▷  $\mathcal{O}(Vk \log k)$ 
for  $n = 1 : k$  do                                     ▷  $\mathcal{O}(k \cdot \mathcal{O}(\cdot))$ 
     $p = \mathcal{P}.\text{pop}()$                                    ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
    if  $p.\text{getWeight}() == 0$  then                       ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
        break
    end if
     $\mathcal{L}.\text{append}(p)$                                      ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$ 
     $c = p.\text{nextBestChild}(W, \mathcal{J}, \underline{\alpha}_+, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{P})$ 
                                                ▷  $\mathcal{O}(V(\log V + \log k))$ 
     $\mathcal{P}.\text{insert}(c)$                                    ▷  $\mathcal{O}(\log k)$ 
     $s = p.\text{nextBestSibling}(W, \mathcal{J}, \underline{\alpha}_+, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{P})$ 
                                                ▷  $\mathcal{O}(V(\log V + \log k))$ 
     $\mathcal{P}.\text{insert}(s)$                                    ▷  $\mathcal{O}(\log k)$ 
end for

```

a) *Initialization of the Tree:* First, the number of sensors V and prior GM components u are extracted. Then, each matrix $\underline{W}_j \in W$ is cut after k columns since solutions containing elements after the k -th column can never belong to the k best solutions. Then, *initSortedIndicesList* creates the sorted list of indices, depending on the best solution of each matrix \underline{W}_j . This list is then taken to create the root node and added to the list of selected nodes \mathcal{L} . The root node can be seen as a dummy node since it does not contain a real solution and is only a necessary placeholder for the connection to other nodes with another GM component id. It has, per definition, the overall highest product weight. Afterward, the potential selection list \mathcal{P} is initialized with the next best child of the root node.

b) *Find k Best Selections:* This part of the algorithm is the same as the *kBestSelection* algorithm with the difference that the calculation of the next best child or sibling must consider whether it is the root node. Therefore, the procedure for calculating the *nextBestChild* or *nextBestSibling* differs from the *kBestSelection* algorithm. As an example, the pseudocode for the algorithm *nextBestChild* is given in Algorithm 2. If the parent node is the root node, then the next best child is calculated using the next best index of the indices list \mathcal{J} . In all other cases, the next best child is calculated via the *nextBestChild* algorithm of the *kBestSelection* algorithm. The algorithm ends when either k solutions have been found, or the next potential solution has a weight of 0.

Algorithm 2: nextBestChild% *GeneralizedKBestSelection*

Input: $W, \mathcal{J}, \underline{\alpha}_+, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{P}$ **Output:** c % child node

```
# generalized nextBestChild algorithm ▷  
 $\mathcal{O}(V(\log V + \log k))$   
 $V = \text{size}(W_1, 1) = \dots = \text{size}(W_u, 1)$  ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$   
if isRootNode() then ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$   
  # Parent Node = RootNode  
  isRootNode = False ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$   
   $j = \mathcal{J}.\text{pop}()$  ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$   
   $c = \text{createNode}(\text{ones}(V, 1), j, \text{isRootNode})$  ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$   
else ▷  $\mathcal{O}(V(\log V + \log k))$   
  # normal kBestSelection case  
   $j = \text{getParentIndex}()$  ▷  $\mathcal{O}(1)$   
   $c = \text{nextBestChild}(W_j, \underline{\alpha}_+(j), \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{P})$  % kBestSelection  
  ▷  $\mathcal{O}(V(\log V + \log k))$   
end if
```

2) *Optimality:*

Proposition 1. *Given a set of u row-wise sorted weight matrices $W = \{W_1, \dots, W_u\}$ with indices $1, \dots, u$, then the proposed algorithm yields the k solutions with highest product weight of A and also is optimal.*

Proof: Like the *kBestSelection* algorithm, the proof is done using mathematical induction.

a) *Base case:* Since the root node as a dummy node has the highest product weight by definition, there cannot be another node with an even higher product weight. Therefore, it represents the global best solution. Since the individual matrices of W are also sorted by weight, the first column provides the highest product weight for the respective GM id j due to the multiplication's monotonicity and corresponds to the best solution in each case. Since the indices list \mathcal{J} , sorted by the highest weights, is used to determine the next best child of the root node, this next child represents the second best global solution. Additionally, it is included in the potential selection list.

b) *Induction step:* Similar to [6], the monotonicity of multiplication, combined with the fact that the root node is defined to have the highest weight, ensures that a child's product weight is always less than or equal to that of its parent. Following the same arguments as in [6], one can show that there cannot exist a node N_{j_n} in the unexplored tree that represents the next best global solution and is not in the list of potentially selected nodes \mathcal{P} .

C. *Computational Complexity*

The complexity of the *kBestSelection* algorithm applied to the case of the fusion of spatial single-sensor posterior densities for one GM component id is given by $\mathcal{O}(kV(\log V + \log k))$. This differs from the complexity given in [6] since, in this case, k and V have similar orders of magnitude. Combined for all prior GM component id's,

Fig. 5. Ground truth trajectories of the objects in the observed area, with start points marked by circles and end points marked by unfilled triangles. The filled triangles (red and black) mark the sensor positions.

the complexity is given by

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\sum_{j=1}^u k_j V(\log V + \log k_j)\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\stackrel{k_1 \approx \dots \approx k_j}{\leq} \mathcal{O}(ukV(\log V + \log k)). \quad (6)$$

In comparison, the overall complexity of the *Generalized-KBestSelection* algorithm for the fusion of single-sensor posterior densities equals $\mathcal{O}(u \log u + kV(\log V + \log k))$, which is less complex.

VI. EVALUATION

Two different simulation scenarios are used to evaluate the performance of the proposed efficient implementation of the FPM-LMB filter. Both equal the scenarios given in [6]. The first scenario is a linear scenario and compares the different efficient single-sensor implementations. The second scenario is a bearing-only scenario and mainly compares the two efficient fusion approaches. The results are compared with a IC-LMB filter [8], which also uses the efficient single-sensor implementations. Both filters always share the same parameter settings. We performed all simulations on an AMD Ryzen 7 3800X processor.

A. *Simulation Setup*

Figure 5 shows the basic configuration of both scenarios. Here, ten objects move simultaneously at a constant speed in the observation area of $[-800, 800] \text{ m} \times [-800, 800] \text{ m}$. Both filters use a Constant Velocity (CV) motion model [20] with the sampling interval $T = 1 \text{ s}$, the survival probability $p_S = 0.98$ in the prediction, and the standard deviation of the discrete white noise sequence $\sigma_a = 0.2 \text{ m s}^{-2}$. Besides, the state vector $x = [p_x, v_x, p_y, v_y]$ represents the positions and velocities of the respective track in x and y directions. New tracks can only be initiated in static birth regions $[p_{B,x}^{(i)}, p_{B,y}^{(i)}]$, which are indicated by circles in Fig. 5 and are modeled by an LMB density $\pi_B \left\{ r_B, p_B^{(i)} \right\}_{i=1}^6$, where $r_B = 0.1$ and $p_B^{(i)} = \mathcal{N}\left(x; x_B^{(i)}, Q_B\right)$ with covariance $Q_B = \text{diag}([10 \text{ m}, 5 \text{ m s}^{-2}, 10 \text{ m}, 5 \text{ m s}^{-2}])^2$ for the first scenario and covariance $Q_B = \text{diag}([15 \text{ m}, 5 \text{ m s}^{-2}, 15 \text{ m}, 5 \text{ m s}^{-2}])^2$ for the second scenario. The state vector for a birth track is

TABLE I

AVERAGE OF GOSPA VALUES OF THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THE FPM-LMB FILTER AND IC-LMB FILTER FOR THE LINEAR SCENARIO

		Scenario	GOSPA (m)	Loc. (m)	Missed ($\cdot 10^{-2}$)	False ($\cdot 10^{-2}$)
2 sensors	IC-LMB	baseline	2.98	3.91	9.60	13.84
		<i>kBest.</i> , no grouping	2.98	3.9	9.63	13.82
		Gibbs, no grouping	3.02	3.86	12.36	11.66
		<i>kBest.</i> , grouping	2.97	3.85	12.11	10.83
		Gibbs, grouping	3.16	3.85	13.32	13.67
	FPM-LMB	baseline	3.23	4.12	8.21	20.36
		<i>kBest.</i> , no grouping	3.25	4.11	8.81	20.10
		Gibbs, no grouping	3.24	3.92	8.85	20.25
		<i>kBest.</i> , grouping	3.3	4.46	7.42	21.73
		Gibbs, grouping	3.37	3.85	7.94	24.27
6 sensors	IC-LMB	baseline	1.72	1.42	9.91	0.14
		<i>kBest.</i> , no grouping	1.72	1.42	9.92	0.14
		Gibbs, no grouping	1.83	1.41	11.93	0.10
		<i>kBest.</i> , grouping	1.73	1.42	10.06	0.16
		Gibbs, grouping	1.71	1.42	9.73	0.10
	FPM-LMB	baseline	1.41	1.555	2.07	2.62
		<i>kBest.</i> , no grouping	1.41	1.557	2.07	2.56
		Gibbs, no grouping	1.32	1.518	2.25	0.66
		<i>kBest.</i> , grouping	1.41	1.58	2.25	2.02
		Gibbs, grouping	1.44	1.55	2.09	2.81

$x_B^{(i)} = [p_{B,x}^{(i)}, 0, p_{B,y}^{(i)}]$. In addition, the objects are detected by either only two (red filled triangles) or all six synchronous omnidirectional sensors, where each sensor has a constant detection probability p_D and Poisson distributed clutter with a mean number of $\lambda_c = 7$ measurements uniformly distributed over the observed area. Furthermore, GM components with a weight lower than $\vartheta_{GM} = 0.001$ are removed. The Murty ranked assignment algorithm calculates the 3000 best updated GLMB hypotheses. Tracks with an existence probability higher than $r^{(\ell)} > 0.5$ are extracted. The results are evaluated using the Generalized Optimal Sub-pattern Assignment metric (GOSPA) [21] with $p = 2$ and $c = 10$. The results of all filters are averaged over 100 Monte Carlo (MC) runs.

B. Linear Scenario

This scenario compares the results of the two filters, focusing on the proposed efficient implementations of the single-sensor LMB updates. For this purpose, five variants are compared per filter: the baseline variant, the *kBestSelection* variants (abbreviated by *kBest.*) with grouping and without grouping, and the Gibbs variants with grouping and without grouping. The baseline variants refer to the filters with the implementation proposed in [8], i.e., they neither use grouping nor the *kBestSelection* algorithm. All variants are evaluated for two and six sensors, which deliver positional measurements with measurement noise covariance $R = \text{diag}([1.5 \text{ m}^2, 1.5 \text{ m}^2])$. A detection probability of $p_D = 0.67$ is used. The Gibbs sampler samples a maximum of 3000 samples and stops sampling if $f = 100$ consecutive samples in a row are sampled. For the transformation from LMB to GLMB densities, the *kBestSelection* algorithm calculates the 2000 best GLMB hypotheses for the variants without grouping and the 5 best GLMB hypotheses for the variants with grouping. For the baseline variants, all GLMB Hypotheses up to the cardinality of $N = 20$ are calculated. Above, the 2000 best hypotheses using the *kBestSelection* algorithm are calculated. Furthermore, tracks with an existence probability

TABLE II

COMPUTATION TIMES OF THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THE FPM-LMB FILTER AND IC-LMB FILTER FOR THE LINEAR SCENARIO

Scenario	IC-LMB (2 sensors)	FPM-LMB (2 sensors)	IC-LMB (6 sensors)	FPM-LMB (6 sensors)
baseline	1831.38 ms	874.21 ms	224.8 ms	75.28 ms
<i>kBest.</i> , no grouping	53.13 ms	30.85 ms	96.66 ms	27.40 ms
Gibbs, no grouping	16.69 ms	12.08 ms	14.35 ms	7.85 ms
<i>kBest.</i> , grouping	7.52 ms	6.31 ms	16.61 ms	7.11 ms
Gibbs, grouping	6.03 ms	4.88 ms	13.29 ms	6.64 ms

TABLE III

COMPUTATION TIMES OF THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THE FPM-LMB FILTER AND IC-LMB FILTER FOR THE BEARING ONLY SCENARIO

IC-LMB	FPM-LMB <i>kBestSelection</i>	FPM-LMB <i>GeneralizedKBestSelection</i>
106.56 ms	67.62 ms	59.51 ms

lower than $\vartheta_r = 0.001$ are removed.

The results are given in Table I. Overall, it can be seen that the FPM-LMB filter variants have far fewer missed tracks compared to the IC-LMB variants. In contrast, the FPM-LMB filter variants tend to have many more false tracks. This is especially the case around birth and death times. The latter only applies to the two sensor cases and leads to the slightly worse GOSPA values of the FPM-LMB filter for the two sensor cases. This behavior has already been mentioned in [8]. Furthermore, it is noticeable that, especially in the two-sensor case, the Gibbs variant with grouping tends to set up too many tracks at birth for both filter types. This is probably due to the approximation caused by sampling and grouping. In the six-sensor cases, the FPM-LMB variants outperform the IC-LMB variants, which is related to the sensor order dependency. The order dependency is especially noticeable for the Gibbs variant without grouping. Otherwise, the results of the different variants per filter type are comparable.

Considering the results of the calculation times in Table II, it is noticeable that all FPM-LMB filter variants outperform the IC-LMB variants due to the parallel calculation of the update. It can also be seen that grouping significantly reduces computational effort. The Gibbs sampling-based approaches are the fastest for all filters.

C. Bearing Only Scenario

This scenario is likely the most challenging due to the enormous ambiguity of the measurement assignments. Therefore, it is ideal for working out the differences between the two proposed efficient fusion implementations of the FPM-LMB filter. In this scenario, the six bearing-only sensors have a detection probability of $p_D = 0.85$ and the measurements are Gaussian distributed with $\mathcal{N}(z^{(s)}; h(x, p^{(s)}), \sigma_a^2)$ with $h(x, p^{(s)}) = \arctan2(x - p_x^{(s)} / y - p_y^{(s)})$ and standard deviation $\sigma_a = \pi/180$ rad. In addition, the $k = 15$ best GM components are calculated using both the *GeneralizedKBestSelection* and the *kBestSelection* algorithm. Besides, all filters use the grouping mentioned in Section IV, and the Murty ranked assignment algorithm is used for the GLMB update. Hypothesis calculation for the conversion from LMB to GLMB density is performed for cardinalities above $N = 18$ using

Fig. 6. Cardinality estimation and GOSPA error for the Bearing Only Scenario averaged over 100 simulation runs. The $kBestSelection$ algorithm is abbreviated with $kBest.$, and the $GeneralizedKBestSelection$ algorithm is abbreviated with $GKBest.$

the $kBestSelection$ algorithm. The 100000 best hypotheses are calculated. Furthermore, tracks with an existence probability lower than $\vartheta_r = 1e^{-8}$ are removed.

As shown in Fig. 6, calculating the actual k best solutions pays off since the fusion approach based on the $GeneralizedKBestSelection$ algorithm performs best. The poor result of the IC-LMB filter is caused by the sensor order dependency, which leads to a poor cardinality estimation and, therefore, a bad GOSPA result. An improvement in the result can only be achieved with more computing time. As already shown in [8], it can also be seen here that the approaches of the FPM-LMB filter at the birth times tend to lead to an overestimation of the cardinality, which is due to the static birth model. The computation times given in Table III show that the two FPM-LMB filter variants are faster by 37% and 44%, respectively, compared to the IC-LMB filter. In addition, the $GeneralizedKBestSelection$ variant is faster than the $kBestSelection$ variant, which confirms the theoretical results in Section V-C.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes and compares several efficient implementations for the FPM-LMB filter. These include the use of the $kBestSelection$ algorithm, a new approximation option for the transformation of LMB to GLMB densities. In addition, a new approach for solving the specific k shortest path problem was developed for the fusion of the FPM-LMB filter using the $GeneralizedKBestSelection$ algorithm. This approach showed a low computational complexity and the best tracking performance, even in demanding scenarios. Furthermore, we have shown in detail that the use of grouping, as well as the use of a Gibbs sampler, greatly reduces the computational effort. Furthermore, all efficient implementations of the FPM-LMB filter outperform the

respective efficient implementations of the IC-LMB filter in terms of computational efficiency and tracking performance.

In future work, we will develop a suitable dynamic birth model for the FPM-LMB filter and then apply the filter to real-world applications.

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